

Deliverable D1.3 Communication and Outreach Strategy Plan

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Authors	Sudeep Das, Maria Mirza
Contributors	Aastha Mathur
Reviewers	Dorothea Dörr, Laurent Chmiel

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GBI	Global BioImaging
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MicroAU	Microscopy Australia
NIF	National Imaging Facility Australia
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructures

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Executive Summary

The successful implementation of the foundingGIDE project depends on clear and effective communication among its 7 partners from 5 countries across 3 continents. The project duration is 2.5 years with a budget of 1.5 million EUR under the HORIZON Europe Coordination and Support Actions (CSA). The project focuses on laying the foundations of a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE) which will facilitate data sharing across bioimage infrastructures in Europe, Japan and Australia, and promote good practices for image data management across the globe. This document outlines the communication and outreach strategy essential for achieving all project objectives and includes a detailed plan for dissemination and engagement. The document addresses diverse audiences, including life science researchers, imaging communities, developers, industry, policymakers, and the general public. It covers project branding, outreach assets, tools for stakeholder engagement, and methods for tracking the impact of dissemination activities. The Communication and Outreach Strategy Plan is envisioned as a living document and will be regularly updated to maximise wider outreach and impact.

1. Communication and Outreach Objectives

The foundingGIDE project will facilitate data sharing across bioimage and preclinical imaging infrastructures in Europe, Japan and Australia, and promote good practices for image data management across the globe. The objectives of foundingGIDE project are to establish coordination among global open bioimage data resources, increase resource interoperability, engage with community initiatives and end-users, plan for sustainability and build an ecosystem for new resources to grow.

The community outreach and communication strategy is hence crucial to build a connected and informed imaging community, in Europe and beyond, that actively contributes to and benefits from foundingGIDE initiatives, fostering a more interoperable image data ecosystem.

The outreach and communication activities have specific objectives:

1) **Raise Awareness and Visibility:** Enhance the visibility of foundingGIDE and its initiatives among Raising the overall profile of the project and helping stakeholders grasp its significance, benefits, and how it relates to the global bioimaging community.

2) **Inform and Educate:** Disseminating accurate and timely information about the project's goals, progress, achievements, challenges, and impacts to all relevant stakeholders. The aim is to create a shared understanding and keep everyone informed.

3) **Boost Global Community Engagement and Collaboration:** Engage the global bioimaging community to participate in and contribute to foundingGIDE

4) **Drive Global Adoption of Developed Solutions:** Promote the adoption and integration of the common ontologies and harmonised metadata developed by foundingGIDE within the global bioimaging community.

5) **Mitigate risks and address concerns:** Proactive communication to help identify and address potential issues, misunderstandings, or resistance early on. It allows for timely responses to criticisms or negative perceptions.

6) **Collaboration and partnerships:** Effective communication to identify opportunities for collaboration, attract new partners, and strengthen existing relationships.

All project partners will leverage their existing projects, network of Nodes and communities to increase the reach and dissemination of foundingGIDE outcomes. Our partners in Japan and Australia will capitalise on their local and regional networks to engage with various stakeholders. Additionally, the Global BioImaging (GBI) network will be crucially involved to extend our reach globally, beyond the project partners.

2. Target audiences

Stakeholder Group	Role	Engagement method
Life Science Researchers	Proper documentation of image data	Partner RIs' user base, training supports, Data Stewards, RDM specialists, GIDE community events
Imaging Scientists and Core Facility Personnel	Technical execution and data handling practices	Feedback on standards feasibility and adoption

Data Stewards and RDM Specialists	Guidelines and support for data management following FAIR principles	Train-the-trainer type training on project outcomes
Imaging Communities and Networks	Image data standardisation (potentially domain specific)	FoundingGIDE's community liaisons, GBI, MicroAU
Non-imaging Communities and RIs	Promote multimodal technologies and image data usage	Life Science RI network, EURO-BIOIMAGING, MicroAU, NIF
Image Data Repository Owners	Implement common ontologies and harmonised metadata	Inclusion in FoundingGIDE technical events
Industry Partners	Ensure compatibility of commercial instruments with standards	Existing industry relations of partners, Euro-BioImaging ERIC's Industry Board ¹ , QUAREP-LiMi ²
Funders and Policymakers	Support policy and infrastructure for data interoperability and accessibility in bioimaging research	Dissemination through EOSC and other initiatives as well as through target-specific policy meetings and events
General Public	Demonstrate project outcomes and impact	Success stories, shared datasets, image data visualisations and contribution to science for citizens events and initiatives

3. Design elements for communication

A strong branding has been created to give the project a unique identity and build relationships with various stakeholders. It provides the consortium members with assets to facilitate their use for internal and external purposes. The [communication package](#) is available in the project document storage.

Logo

The logo symbolises the convergence and integration of various bioimage data formats with inward-pointing arrows. These arrows also represent global collaboration, with many partners uniting for a common purpose. An upward and forward-pointing arrow signifies progress and the guidance foundingGIDE provides in data interoperability. The modern design and contrasting colour palette suggest innovation and a forward-thinking mindset, reflecting foundingGIDE's dedication to open access, cooperation, and sustainable use of imaging data.

¹ <https://www.eurobioimaging-industryboard.com/>

² <https://quarep.org/>

The logo pack is available in RGB colour mode for digital display and CMYK colour mode for printing. The images are available to partners in .svg, .png, .jpg and .ai formats for ready incorporation into a variety of materials.

Apart from foundingGIDE logo, the project partners have also been made aware of their legal obligations to acknowledge EU funding and display the EU emblem in all information and communication material.³ This was particularly important for us to emphasise since the project has partners from Australia and Japan who are less accustomed to working on EU funded projects. This was planned and implemented since the start of the project and is reflected in the templates that have been provided for presentations, posters and project deliverables.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

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Guidelines

Guidelines for creating materials are available in the communications package and follow EU guidelines.⁴ Chosen fonts for the project are Inter (fonts.google.com) Albert Sans (fonts.google.com). The colour palette for the project is available as hex codes. Tints and shades for the primary colours can be created as required from online tint and shade generators.

PRIMARY COLORS

HEX #2DE2D9
RGB 45 226 217
CMYK 70 0 25 0

HEX #FF8C3E
RGB 255 140 62
CMYK 0 50 80 0

HEX #282828
RGB 20 20 20
CMYK 0 0 0 93

HEX #ffffff
RGB 255 255 255
CMYK 0 0 0 0

SECONDARY COLORS

HEX #C5E68A
RGB 197 230 138
CMYK 30 0 56 0

HEX #ffd3c
RGB 32 36 40
CMYK 0 20 80 0

Texts and presentation material

In order to ease the usage of text in communications, foundingGIDE provides some boilerplate text and key messages that can be reused in different contexts. In the “About us” section of the foundingGIDE website, boilerplate texts exist as shown below:

⁴ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/communication-toolkit_en

As a start, presentation materials are available to be used by all project partners which include a 1 slide introduction, foundingGIDE poster and slides presented at Euro-BioImaging's All Hands Nodes Meeting^{5,6}.

Giveaways

Giveaways like flyers, stickers, bottles, pens, bags, etc. with foundingGIDE branding have been designed. Some of these materials will be produced and distributed at events organised by foundingGIDE stakeholders to raise awareness about the project and help build a community. The decisions on producing the giveaways will be made while being mindful of the environmental impact that they could have.

4. Outreach, dissemination and exploitation

Given the global scope of our target audiences, using various channels and tools is essential for successful communication of project outcomes and engagement. Outreach activities aim to create continuously relevant content in order to illustrate how the community can contribute and benefit from foundingGIDE. As mentioned earlier, the [communication package](#) is available in the project document storage to assist in the creation of the outreach material.

⁵ <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/wp-content/uploads/All-Hands-Nodes-Meeting-2024-final-program.pdf>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11108346>

4.1 Website

The website for foundingGIDE was created and hosted by Euro-BioImaging and is linked below:

<https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/>

The website summarises the challenges that led to the project and how the project aims to coordinate among the global research infrastructures enabling bioimage data exchange. The target audience for the website is wide as the website often serves as the first contact that people have with the project. The foundingGIDE logo has been displayed at the top and the bottom of the webpage. The webpage currently has five primary sections: Home, About us, Community, Events and News. The bottom of the webpage is always constant in any subpage and contains webpage links, social media links (Twitter/X and LinkedIn), foundingGIDE email (foundingGIDE@eurobioimaging.eu), link to newsletter signup sheet, privacy policy of the webpage, consent preferences, EU logo and acknowledgement text for the funding provided by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Both the foundingGIDE logo and the EU funding logo are on the website frame which appears on all sections.

In the "About us" section the project describes the consortium objectives and emphasises its role in coordination between research infrastructures in the EU and those in Japan and Australia. All partner logos are displayed to help the audience recognise their branding, increase their visibility and promote future partnerships. The structure describes how the Work Packages are organised into different Themes to achieve their specific goals.

The "Community" section describes the key target audience of foundingGIDE. It also outlines opportunities for engagement and synergy with the project, as well as benefits for the larger community.

The "Events" section lists all the events that are relevant to our target audience, including Life scientists, data managers and the global imaging community. The upcoming events and past events are listed with an option to sign up to the foundingGIDE calendar.

The “News” section contains news articles about recent activities, events, achievements, and developments within the FoundingGIDE project. The news releases coincide with other social media articles and with an update to the foundingGIDE Dissemination registry as described later.

4.2 Newsletters

Newsletters will be released quarterly to summarise the activities that have taken place and update on relevant future items. There might also be *ad hoc* communications if there are items which need immediate attention. All the published newsletters will be available on the news section of the [foundingGIDE website](#). The foundingGIDE related content for the newsletter will be requested from all project partners and final material will be created and published by Euro-BioImaging.

The link to the newsletter sign up is bit.ly/foundingGIDE-newsletter. The GDPR compliant registration form is used to collect contact information and is open to anyone who consents to having their data stored and accessible to the project management team for the duration of the project and the retention period established by the EC. The link is also posted on the foundingGIDE website.

4.3 Social media channels

foundingGIDE has the following social media accounts:

Social media channel	Account link
LinkedIn	http://www.linkedin.com/company/foundinggide/
Bluesky	https://bsky.app/profile/gideproject.bsky.social
X	https://twitter.com/GIDEproject

These platforms were chosen as they are the most popular among professionals and bioimage enthusiasts. The plan is to promote and share relevant activities directly linked to the project or related content of interest to the bioimage community. The content is shared more frequently in [Bluesky](#), whereas on LinkedIn, posts/reposts are capped at two times per week. These channels allow us to connect with other relevant EU-funded projects and community initiatives in the image data space and share outputs. We have scaled back on our X coverage since late 2024.

4.4 Events

The community events will encourage exchanges between various bioimage resource owners, maintainers, developers, and other relevant stakeholders. There will be at least 3 community events with around 150 participants per event. A community event will have at least 5 imaging communities and at least 5 image data resources represented per event.

The Community event organised by WP2 will bring together the stakeholders, including the project partners and their extended global collaborators. The second and third events organised by WP3, will take place in Australia and Japan. These locations will allow us to reach out to researchers associated with our partner RIs, including communities and topics of local interest and hence ensure meaningful participation of global partners in the project.

A report summarising participation, engagement and outreach achieved through GIDE community events will be provided as deliverable D3.1, and it will help assess the impact of the project and guide the organisation of such events in future.

To further enhance the reach and visibility of the project, foundingGIDE representatives will actively participate in various imaging community events such as European Light Microscopy Initiative (ELMI) and Trends in Microscopy (TiM). This engagement will improve the understanding of the communities' needs, challenges, and solutions related to image data management. The goal is to identify synergies and collaboration opportunities, demonstrating how the community can contribute to the outcomes of the GIDE project. Additionally, this will facilitate the effective adoption of GIDE's outcomes by these communities, ultimately working towards achieving a global image data ecosystem.

The project Dissemination registry is used to track dissemination activity filled by all project partners.

4.5 Publications

Publications, presentations and other outputs created by the foundingGIDE project will be tracked using the foundingGIDE Dissemination registry. All project partners will be able to upload materials to Zenodo's general-purpose data repository built on open-source software and available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/gide>. DOI created for publications will be used for proper citation and to assess the reach and the impact of the outputs. Metadata standards and ontologies developed in the project will be shared openly and indexed in the FAIRsharing resource (fairsharing.org). These recommendations will be documented and published on open resources, like GitHub, enabling community development. The project website or social media channels will share all relevant links and developments.

All project publications will acknowledge the funding agency using the following paragraph:

foundingGIDE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101130216. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4.6 Strategy

The FoundingGIDE project's dissemination strategy is multifaceted, aiming to ensure broad reach, engagement, and impact across various stakeholders. Central to this strategy is the extensive promotion of the development and extension of open standards for image data harmonisation, focusing on ontologies and metadata. These standards, documented on open resources like GitHub and FAIRsharing, will facilitate adoption, sharing, and further development by the community. This open-access approach ensures that the project's recommendations are easily consultable and can be engaged with by experts globally. This approach will ensure that the benefits of the project outcomes are not limited to the partners or their immediate connections, but are available to a global audience.

Additionally, the project will produce tools for image data search and metadata recording, making them openly available along with comprehensive supporting documentation. To maximise the utility of these tools, developer and training events will be organised to raise awareness on their practical application and demonstrate their utility. Educational materials, particularly on ontologies and metadata usage, will be a significant output, with at least two workshops hosted either virtually, in hybrid formats or as satellite events at relevant conferences. These workshops aim to ensure widespread participation and leverage the training capabilities of project partners, disseminating materials through platforms like the Global BioImaging training resource.

Enhancing data discoverability is another critical aspect, achieved by agreeing on a common data catalogue. This will make image data easily discoverable through generic services like openAIRE⁷,

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

integrated within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁸. This initiative not only increases visibility within the life sciences but also extends to other research fields. The project will also exploit strong communication channels within the Life Science Research Infrastructures (RI) network to amplify the impact of image data dissemination.

Outreach efforts will include at least two technical events and three community events, targeting both developers and imaging scientists. These events, widely publicised through the extensive network of partners, including Global BioImaging, aim to ensure global community participation and inclusivity, especially towards under-represented communities. The project will leverage its extensive partner network to expand its reach and influence policy, facilitating the acceptance of project outputs by a large, cross-disciplinary community. Strong relationships between RIs like Euro-BioImaging and its national Nodes across Europe and other project partners' networks will bolster engagement in policy events.

A coherent communication strategy will be supported by the project's visual identity, branding, and templates, alongside branded communication materials for promoting workshops, hackathons, and other events. These materials will be part of a dynamically growing dissemination toolkit available to all partners. The foundingGIDE website hosted by Euro-BioImaging will be a key communication platform, providing an up-to-date overview of the project, its partners, publications, news, and events. This website will also feature interviews with consortium partners, members of the Scientific Advisory Board, and external experts, ensuring ongoing public engagement.

To ensure efficient resource use, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities will be strategically planned and combined with related events to promote stakeholder interaction and minimise the carbon footprint. This has been implemented in the planning of the first foundingGIDE community event and the foundingGIDE Hackathon back to back after the GBI event in fall of 2024.

The current DEC plan will be periodically updated in line with project progress, discussed at annual consortium meetings, and stored on the project intranet for partner access. This comprehensive and adaptive approach ensures that dissemination efforts remain aligned with the project's evolving needs and goals.

4.7 KPIs to measure impact

To measure the effectiveness and impact of the foundingGIDE project's dissemination strategy, a robust set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been established. The table below outlines the specific KPIs, their related work packages (WPs), and estimated measures.

Category	Related WP(s)	Related KPIs	Estimated Measure
Project webpage	1	Engagement analytics from the webpage	-

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/>

Social media	1	Number of social media accounts maintained	At least 2
		Social media analytics from different platforms	
Policy events	1	Number of policy events attended	At least 1
GIDE coordination events	2,3	Number of events	At least 3
		Number of participants per event	Around 150
		Number of imaging communities represented per event	At least 5
		Number of image data resources represented per event	At least 5
GIDE technical events	2	Number of events (or satellite events)	At least 2
		Number of participants per event	Around 50
		Number of technical communities represented per event	At least 5
		Number of image data resources represented per event	At least 5
Community outreach	9	Number of external community events attended	At least 4
		Number of non-imaging communities engaged	At least 3
Training / Workshops	9	Number of training / workshops organised/supported	At least 2
Metadata / data search tools	11, 12	Number of tools made openly available	At least 2
Publications	All	Number of publications made openly available	At least 3

These KPIs align with the project's strategic goals and ensure that various aspects of dissemination, community engagement, and technical development are effectively monitored. The estimated

measures provide clear targets to strive towards, facilitating continuous assessment and necessary adjustments throughout the project's lifespan. This structured approach to tracking KPIs will enable the foundingGIDE project to maintain its focus on impactful dissemination and broad community engagement, ensuring long-term success and sustainability.

5. Project Communication and External Outreach KPI Report (January 2024 - May 2025)

This update summarizes the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) metrics collected for the project's website and social media channels over the last 18 months, specifically from **January 2024 to May 2025**. The analysis is based on the desired KPI indicators outlined in the project's deliverable documentation.

5.1. Webpage Performance

Engagement analytics from the webpage

Over the 18-month period, the project website recorded a total of **1013 website visits/clicks**. This metric provides a high-level overview of overall user engagement and reach of the project's online presence. While no specific target was set for this KPI, this baseline allows for future comparisons and assessment of growth in website visibility and user interest. In addition our website visibility has increased as it appears in more searches.

Website engagement - Clicks

Website visibility

5.2. Newsletter Performance

Engagement analytics from the newsletters

A total of 171 newsletter sign-ups were registered across four periods. Our [newsletters](#) have been published quarterly as planned and we are reaching out to a respectable number of people in the community.

Newsletter Subscribers, Opens and Clicks

5.3. Social Media Performance

The project successfully maintained **3** active social media accounts, which are: **X (formerly Twitter)**, **LinkedIn**, and **Bluesky**. This meets and exceeds the desired KPI of maintaining at least 2 social media accounts, demonstrating a commitment to a multi-platform social media strategy. We have scaled back our efforts on the X platform as the community has shifted towards Bluesky and X analytics has been available only to paid accounts since mid-2024. The imaging data community has been active in the Bluesky platform, and consequently, we have also been active on that platform since early 2025.

Detailed analytics from each platform provide insights into the project's reach and audience growth.

- **X (formerly Twitter):**
 - **Latest Follower Count (September 2024):** 117 followers
- **LinkedIn:**
 - **Latest Follower Count (May 2025):** 253 followers
- **Bluesky:**
 - **Latest Follower Count (May 2025):** 140 followers

Social Media Engagement

The consistent growth in followers across all platforms indicates increasing visibility and interest in the project's activities within these online communities.

5.4. Summary

The project has made good progress in its communication and outreach efforts during the reporting period. The maintenance of three social media platforms surpasses the set target, and all platforms show positive follower growth, indicating a growing audience. The website has also garnered a significant number of visits, establishing a foundational online presence. This M18 update to the D1.3 serves as a foundational analysis of the project's communication and outreach, showing strong confirmation to our strategy to reach our target audience through the communication and outreach efforts.

Conclusion

The foundingGIDE project is poised to significantly advance the global bioimaging community by implementing the comprehensive DEC strategy that supports its ambitious objectives. Through the strategic dissemination of open standards, tools, and educational materials, the project will facilitate harmonisation of image data across international repositories, and provide data management guidelines to individual researchers. Key to this effort is the creation of openly accessible resources and tools that not only enhance data discoverability but also encourage widespread adoption and engagement among researchers, developers, and policymakers.

The project has planned technical and community events, which will be essential for driving the adoption of its solutions and expanding its influence. By leveraging the extensive networks of its partners and utilising robust communication platforms, such as the Euro-BioImaging hosted website, FoundingGIDE will ensure its outputs reach a diverse and global audience.

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